

SURVEILLANCE CARDS_CCHF_Pathogen detection in ticks collected from migratory birds in high-risk regions and seasons

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in ticks collected from migratory birds in high-risk regions and seasons.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen. Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas.
3	Target species and group	<i>Hyalomma spp ticks</i> (mainly <i>H. marginatum</i>).
4	Target sector / production type	Migratory birds (mainly passerine birds).
5	Geographical area covered	High-risk areas with regards to introduction of disease and presence of ticks (climate, vegetation). Areas free from CCHF with presence of ticks and sufficiently high temperatures in spring to allow for development of infected nymphs carried by migratory birds.
6	Age group	Immature ticks.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Ticks from migratory birds collected from birds found dead or caught for ringing.
8	Sampling time period	Period when relevant migratory birds return to the region (spring).
9	Sampling matrix	Immature <i>Hyalomma spp</i> ticks entering the country on migratory birds.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus.
11	Sampling unit	Ticks.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Convenience sampling of birds caught or collected for other surveillance components.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Pooling by animal/location/life stage –pool of max 5 half ticks (other half for virus isolation & prevalence). Antigen testing by RT-PCR.

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component can contribute to detection of introduction of the virus in new areas. However, results cannot be used directly for estimation of detection sensitivity or confidence of freedom since this is a biased (non-representative) sample of an unknown population.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	West Nile Virus (testing of passerine birds).
18	References	<p>1) Cicculi V, Maitre A, Ayhan N, Mondoloni S, Paoli JC, Vial L, de Lamballerie XN, Charrel R, Falchi A. Lack of Evidence for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus in Ticks Collected from Animals, Corsica, France. <i>Emerg Infect Dis.</i> 2022 May;28(5):1035-1038. doi: 10.3201/eid2805.211996. PMID: 35447051; PMCID: PMC9045455.</p> <p>2) Mazzola LT, Kelly-Cirino C. Diagnostic tests for Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever: a widespread tickborne disease. <i>BMJ Glob Health.</i> 2019 Feb 20;4(Suppl 2):e001114. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001114. PMID: 30899574; PMCID: PMC6407549.</p>
19	Additional comments	The rate of CCHFV-infected ticks in countries in Europe with enzootic foci ranges from 0.50% to 3.70% among <i>Hyalomma</i> spp. ticks (1)